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California State University, Los Angeles

PEDIATRIC EARLY WARNING SCORES (PEWS) TOOL IMPLEMENTATION: A
QUALITY IMPROVEMENT PROJECT ON A PEDIATRIC UNIT

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

Shelley Burke

Doctoral Project Committee Approval:

Asma Taha, PhD, RN, CPNP-PC/AC, FAAN, Team Leader
Rebecca Sandoval, DNP, RN, MBA, NE-BC, Team Member

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Author Note

Shelley Burke - <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3965-4074>
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ABSTRACT

Purpose/Objective: The aim of this quality improvement project was to facilitate the implementation of the Pediatric Early Warning System (PEWS) in a general pediatric unit. **Background:** Various illnesses can affect a child's health condition. When a child becomes ill, especially with a respiratory illness, they are at risk of deteriorating quickly. Children who are sick need to be monitored closely, so signs and symptoms of distress can be caught early before a child's condition deteriorates or even dies. Assessment skills are crucial in identifying deterioration and changes in a child's health status. A child on the decline requires prompt intervention to prevent unexpected death. There are benefits to early referral and recognition of respiratory distress signs, the key to timely care. Consequently, the nurse needs a clear understanding of the difference between distress and normal physiology in the child, so that essential and appropriate care can be implemented, leading to positive outcomes. **Methodology:** Utilizing an appreciative inquiry framework, this improvement project entails three phases. In phase 1, a focus group was conducted to assess strengths, opportunities, barriers, and resources available for the use of the PEWS. In phase 2, findings of the focus group provided strategies for the systematic implementation of the PEWS. Phases 1 and 2 near completion. For phase 3, retrospective chart reviews to assess nurses' utilization of the PEWS tool are ongoing. **Results:** First phase findings show that the focus group is highly motivated to use evidence-based tools in providing clinical care. Medical and administrative teams were in support of changes in practice. Using a Strength, Opportunities, Aspiration, Results (SOAR) analysis, the core values of the unit were identified and included supportive leadership, motivation to change, desire to use evidence-based practice and to increase commonality in communication. In phase 2, 36 nursing staff (3 male, 33 females) participated in the PEWS education. One third of nurses was under five years into their nursing careers and one third have over 20 years in the field. Furthermore, development of an online module has been proposed to the unit manager and is under consideration. In phase 3, an analysis of up to 60 random patients' charts showed that utilization increased from 1.6 ± 0.2 (mean \pm SEM) 'yes' responses from up to four patients charts per day audited over seven days before PEWS education to 3.6 ± 0.2 charts audited over eight days after PEWS education; $p < 0.0001$, unpaired T-test. This is an increase of $\sim 125\%$ and is an indication that the goal of utilizing the PEWS tool was achieved in the immediacy of post-PEWS education. The process of monitoring ongoing patient assessment and providing additional support for the team will continue over the next five months. **Conclusion:** Patient assessment is a crucial part of care delivery. Nursing and medical staff commitment to change and best practices is crucial in designing, implementing, and evaluating quality improvement projects in patient care areas. Evidence-based devices such as the PEWS tool help to enhance clinician's performance in the assessment and care of children.

Keywords: children, pediatric early warning score, PEWS tool

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Background

There are various illnesses that can affect a child's health. In general, a child's health is very delicate. When a child becomes ill, especially with a respiratory illness, they are at risk of deteriorating quickly. Children who are sick need to be monitored closely, so that signs and symptoms of distress can be caught early before a child's condition deteriorates or dies. Many times, the child's symptoms are unrecognized because a clinician may not be proficient at assessment (Chapman et al., 2010; Lambert et al., 2017). A child on the decline requires prompt intervention to prevent unexpected death. According to Mclellan et al., (2017) and Parshuram et al., (2018) there are benefits to early referral and recognition of signs of respiratory distress, which are key to timely care. Consequently, the nurse needs a clear understanding of the difference between distress and normal physiology in the child, so that essential and appropriate care can be implemented, leading to positive outcomes.

In the United States, the mortality rate for a hospitalized child has not significantly increased over the past years. According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) and the National Center for Health Statistics (NCHS, 2018; Murphy, 2018) there were 21,467 total deaths among children under the age of one. In addition, the infant mortality rate is 566.2 infant deaths per 100,000 live births. This rate is slightly down from 2017, which had a mortality rate of 579.3 infants per 100,000 live births. While these mortality rates are not specific to hospitalized children, they provide a picture of the nation's mortality rate among children. In identifying the impact of mortality among the pediatric population, one can appreciate the benefits of closely monitoring a hospitalized child who may be at risk for clinical deterioration. In addition, there has been a significant decrease in the length of stay for hospitalized children.

In 1997, the average length of stay for a child one year and older was 7.8 days compared to 2017, which was down to 1.7. In children between the ages of six to seventeen, the number of hospital days was 2.3 in 1997 down to 0.3 in 2017 (CDC, 2018). When ethnic groups and insurance status are accounted for, the length of stay in the hospital continues to decrease. The most recent available statistics in 2012 reveal nearly one out of every six children discharged from U.S hospitals were children seventeen year or younger, with most discharges being infants, including newborns. Between the 2008 and 2012, the rate of hospitalizations decreased by 0.6 percent per year among infants and 0.9 percent per year among children. During that same time, hospital costs per stay for infants and children increased 6.7% to 6.4% respectively (Witt et al., 2014).

A variety of factors may explain the trends in hospitalizations among children, which includes changes in health conditions for which children are treated and the type of insurance coverage they have. For most conditions, the rate of hospitalizations for children decreased or remained relatively unchanged during the years 2000 to 2012 (Witt et al., 2014). Respiratory diagnoses such as pneumonia, acute bronchitis, and asthma are the main reasons for hospital stays for children (Witt et al., 2014). Other illnesses or diagnosis requiring hospitalizations include mood disorders, appendicitis, and epilepsy/convulsions (Witt et al., 2014). Children with injuries, acute or debilitating illnesses are frequently admitted to the hospital and require close monitoring. This monitoring involves the use of varied assessment tools and electronic devices, which monitor a child's heart and breathing rates, body temperature and oxygen level (Agulnik et al., 2017). However, these tools and devices are only as good as the nurse who administers them. It is important that accurate assessments are conducted, and results are interpreted for the ongoing monitoring of the findings.

Children who experience in-hospital cardiopulmonary arrest have low survival rates (25-38%) (McLellan et al., 2017). Early recognition and early intervention of critical deterioration may prevent most in-hospital pediatric cardiopulmonary arrests. Although the focus of this project is not directly addressing cardiopulmonary arrest in children, it is worth noting the importance of monitoring the pediatric patient, where there is an indication of clinical deterioration. Similarly, early recognition and early intervention of critical deterioration may prevent most in-hospital pediatric cardiopulmonary arrests from occurring. Early intervention provides a greater opportunity to mitigate the adverse effects of health conditions.

The Pediatric Early Warning Score (PEWS) Scoring Tool was developed to promote early recognition of the deterioration of hospitalized pediatric patients and provide early identification of children who are at risk for respiratory arrest (Brady et al., 2013; McLellan et al., 2017; Seiger et al., 2013). The PEWS is used to capture the physiological changes in pediatric patients suffering from cardiovascular, respiratory, neurobehavioral, or general functioning. As stated by Bell et al. (2013), the use of a standardized method for monitoring a patient's condition offers the best method for assessing care needs. The PEWS provides an assessment for children who may deteriorate quickly depending on their age and are often not able to communicate their needs. The PEWS is an efficient, quick, and easy method for providing a clinical evaluation (de Groot et al., 2018; Thomas-Jones et al., 2018). McElroy et al. (2019) stated that the PEWS Scoring tool helps to improve the recognition of early signs of deterioration among pediatric patients. The PEWS is used both nationally and internationally in many pediatric healthcare departments and is recognized for its practicality and reliability for evaluating the health status of pediatric patients (Gold et al., 2014). Moreover, when compared

with other assessment tools, PEWS was found less likely to introduce bias and may be performed by providers with more basic training (Hansoti et al., 2017).

Problem Statement

The PEWS assessment was introduced a few years ago as a potential assessment for children admitted to the pediatric unit. Although the medical and nursing team were interested in launching the assessment, no systematic implementation plan was used. As a result, the assessment was not integrated into current practices. Currently, the pediatric team is championing a process for implementation and supporting nursing and medical teams throughout the process.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project was to facilitate the implementation of the Pediatrics Early Warning Systems (PEWS) tool for use in a general pediatric unit. The aim of this project was threefold. The first was to assess aspiration, strengths, barriers, and resources to using the tool at a local pediatric department at a Southern California hospital. The second was to develop strategies focused on the systematic implementation of the tool. And, finally, to assess nurses' utilization of the tool over a five-month period after implementation.

Conceptual Framework

A conceptual framework is a catch-all term used to describe classification schemes such as theoretical framework, models, theories, and typologies. It is an explanation of a problem based on related concepts (Badenhorst, 2018). According to Polit and Beck (2017) and Badenhorst (2018), a framework is the overall conceptual underpinnings of a project used to shape it. The framework provides the assumptions that underpin the perspective of the project. In

addition, it provides the rationale for the concepts, and analysis of the relationship between them, as it guides and directs the project. A conceptual framework provides a means to examine the nursing relationships to external factors; thereby, assigning meaning to the practice and organization of a project giving it focus and clarity (Wilson et al., 2015).

Conceptual models provide a perspective regarding interrelated phenomena but are more loosely structured than theories. Conceptual models can serve as springboards for generating hypotheses but not formally tested (Polit & Beck, 2017). They present an understanding of the phenomenon of interest and reflect the views of the model's design. As a model for guiding improvement projects, it defines the relevant variables for the project and plots how they might be related to each other (Wilson et al., 2015).

Institute for Healthcare Improvement (IHI) model - PDSA

This PEWS quality improvement (QI) project utilized the IHI model and the Plan–Do–Study–Act (PDSA) cycle. The PDSA method originated from industry and Walter Shewhart and Edward Deming's articulation of the iterative process, which eventually became known as the four stages of PDSA. The PDSA cycles provide a structure for iterative testing of changes to improve systems quality (Taylor et al., 2014). The method is widely accepted for healthcare improvement and is used in the undertaking of quality improvement projects (Taylor et al., 2014). This model was selected based on the improvement of the scientific literature in healthcare settings. The PDSA model was most appropriate for guiding change in healthcare practices as it allowed for the testing of a small change, provided an opportunity for refinement at each stage, and has the potential to reveal additional areas of improvement (Bittle et al., 2016). This Doctor of Nursing Practice QI project focused on implementing the proposed change in practice using the PSDA cycle and the model to guide the improvement. The PDSA cycle was

used to implement and evaluate changes, testing those changes, and then implementing the changes. Bittle et al., (2016) and Crowfoot et al., (2017) stated that the PDSA model was most helpful in guiding healthcare practices with consistency, education, and standardization.

When considering a QI project in an organization, three fundamental questions must be considered: What are we trying to accomplish? How will we know that a change is an improvement ?; and What changes can be made that results in an improvement? The PDSA Model has four phases, which allows for re-evaluation opportunities while it is being implemented (Provost & Murray, 2011). The Plan phase involves the designing of the project, which will be carried out to address a practice change. The Do phase is the implementation of the practice change. The Study phase is the process of observing and learning from the consequences of the practice change. The Act phase is the determination of the modifications needed to the practice change. Implementing the PDSA Model requires adequate time to be spent on each phase to ensure its efficiency (Provost & Murphy, 2011) and subsequent changes as the project evolves.

The project utilized a QI design and the two-part IHI model, addressing the three specific questions and the second part using the PDSA, a four-stage problem solving model. The PDSA cycles are used to test change determining if there was an improvement. Several cycles of the PDSA Model may be needed to evaluate the implementation process of the PEWS tool.

The IHI Model has two parts. The first part addresses three specific questions. The first question pertains to what the research is trying to accomplish. The use of SMART goals, which is an acronym for Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant and Time bound. The S represents the specific actions that will take place in implementing the PEWS. The M are the quantifiable measures that will be gathered from the PEWS, which is the number of chart audits, completion

of the PEWS and nurse's perception of the use of the PEWS. The A is determining if standardizing the use of the PEWS is achievable in the pediatric unit. The R is determining the relevancy of the PEWS for its ease of use in evaluating children at risk for deterioration. Finally, the T represents the time bound requirements for implementing the PEWS. The use of the PEWS may require additional costs to the unit.

The second question of the IHI Model is how the researchers or clinicians will know that a change was an improvement in practice or outcome. The use of the PEWS should help to identify children at risk of deterioration. Thus, an outcome measure would be a decrease in the number of children who received care early enough to not require advanced care. As use of the PEWS increases, nurses will become more proficient in its use and will lead to improved identification of at-risk children.

The last question pertains to the changes that can be made that will result in an improvement in practice or treatment. The use of the PEWS is a practice change that will help to improve the identification of children at risk for deterioration leading to a high level of care. The PDSA is a four-stage problem solving model. This is the second part of the IHI Model and will be discussed next. Another representation of the PDSA cycle is the sequential knowledge building of ramps where changes are made due to new knowledge, new understanding, and new discoveries. (See Figure 1)

An alternative way to represent the model for change is by the PDSA cycle ramps, sequential building of knowledge. This approach helps the team to design small scale PDSA cycles for initial tests of change, followed by test, adapt, and then implement a change idea (See Figure 2).

Figure 1

The Institute for Healthcare Improvement Model for Improvement

Note. The PDSA cycle- (Batool, 2020). Part 1 of the model shows the three questions asked. Part 2 guides changes to see if there is an improvement. Testing of the change is done using the PDSA cycle.

Figure 2*PDSA Cycle Ramps: Sequential Building of Knowledge*

Note. Pediatric nursing: Scope and standards of practice (2nd ed.). American Nurses Association
The PDSA Cycle Ramp: Sequential building of knowledge. Ramps are typically used to take a very small-scale test and incrementally builds on knowledge.

Phase one, the Plan, is the identification of the problem and the purposed solution to address the situation (IHI, 2015; Provost & Murray, 2011). In this phase, the project question is formulated to drive the planning phase. Many ways have been considered to help realizes this plan. Buy-in from stakeholders, Chief Nurse Officer (CNO), unit director, doctors, charge nurses, educators, nurses, review of current literature, examination of current practices at the institution, as well as similar practices in other similar organizations, chart reviews, and nursing education survey. The purpose of this stage is to gauge nurses' views of the PEWS and their barriers to using it.

The second phase of the PDSA framework is the Do phase, which is to carry out the plan. This phase is the actual implementation of the intervention. During this phase, patients are monitored on equipment which requires ongoing assessment and documentation of their PEWS. It is important that nurses are consistent in their charting of their assessment findings which doctors can use to aide them in their assessment findings as part of their patient's assessment and clinical status. During this phase, the problems encountered are clearly documented, close observation of the process is carried out, and data is gathered.

The third phase is the Study phase of the PDSA framework. The team analyzes the data produced by the intervention (IHI, 2015; Provost & Murray, 2011). The project team observes the roll out of the intervention, gathers data, compares the data to the predictions, and measures the level of success or the presenting barriers and what lessons have been learned during this phase.

The fourth phase of the cycle is the Act phase, this does not mean the completion of the project but is a point in time for determining what modifications if any should be made to the project. There may be several PDSA cycles modifications before the final adoption of the practice change (See Figure 3).

Figure 3*The Plan Do Study Act Model*

Note. The Model shows the four stages of the PDSA cycle (Batool, 2020). The **Plan**: What do we want to accomplish? The **Do**: Carry out the test, document problems and unexpected observations and collect and analyze data. The **Study**: Analyze the results and compare them your prediction, summarize and reflect on what was learned. The **Act**: Based on what was learned from the test, plan for your next step. Adapt, adopt, or abandon. Prepare a plan for the next PDSA.

Review of Literature

A literature review was conducted to examine the state of evidence related to Pediatric Early Warning Systems (PEWS). The literature review consisted of primary and secondary searches. Although the focus is on implementing an identified assessment tool; other concepts such as nurse competencies, communication, and safety are crucial for the comprehensive utilization of clinical tools. These concepts were addressed in the literature review. The literature search utilized three databases: CINAHL, PubMed and Science Direct. These databases were explored using the following key terms: "assessment," "pediatric early warning systems," "trigger tools," "pediatric nurses," "deterioration," "documentation," "communication," "nurse's knowledge," "SBAR," "competence," "confidence," "patient safety," "monitors," "respiratory," and "cardiopulmonary."

The literature search was limited to journal articles published from 2012 to 2020 and in English language only. The reference list of the articles was examined to obtain additional sources of information. Inclusion criteria for articles reviewed were original quantitative research, systematic reviews, and meta-analysis papers. For this review, the fourteen articles that were reviewed evaluated the efficacy of the PEWS. The PEWS was not a substitute for a full clinical assessment and the nurse's clinical judgment. However, it aids in the identification of at-risk pediatric patients who are likely to deteriorate. McElroy et al. (2019) stated that the use of the PEWS for nursing assessment benefited the patient. It helps in early identification, mitigation of risks, and escalation to a higher level of care. Additionally, early warning systems facilitate safety and prompt nurses and doctors to think about the patient's potential for deterioration (Bonafide et al., 2013). The literature indicated that consistency in the use of the PEWS helps to

keep the nurse engaged in monitoring the patient closely to identify changes in the patient's health status or condition (Appendix A).

Pediatric Early Warning Systems (PEWS)

A multidisciplinary group developed the PEWS Scoring Tool at the University Hospitals National Health Services Trust in the United Kingdom. Dr. Alan Monaghan led the project and was the original creator of the PEWS Scoring Tool. The aim was to provide a practical and objective method to identify hospitalized pediatric patients at risk for cardiac arrest (Kwon, 2018; Sefton et al., 2015). The PEWS was similarly described as a reproducible assessment of a child's clinical status while hospitalized (Gold et al., 2014). The Modified Early Warning Systems (MEWS) was the initial version on which the PEWS was based. The MEWS was used for adult patients and was modified to fit the vital parameters and manifestations seen in children. The purpose of the PEWS was to identify pediatric patients at risk of deterioration, to mitigate the risk, apply appropriate clinical and procedural responses, and escalate to a higher level of care if mitigation was unsuccessful (McElroy et al., 2019). The PEWS was adapted for use in multiple settings, including acute pediatric units, PICUs, academic centers, and community hospitals. The PEWS scoring tool was adapted, nationally and internationally, in many pediatric settings. In addition to its practicality, the PEWS supported the nurse's clinical decision-making and provided a common language for effective communication. The tool identified three main clinical assessment categories to monitor: cardiovascular, respiratory, and behavior. In each of these three categories, scores ranged from zero to plus three with a score of zero representing a stable child, while plus three indicated a need for an intervention or escalation to a higher level of care. Color-coded PEWS models make for quicker identification of the assigned ranges in each category. Multiple studies have indicated the tool's usefulness for

aiding with ongoing assessment of pediatric patients (Bell et al., 2013; Jeffery et al., 2018; Jensen et al., 2017). It provided evidence-informed methods to assess children in different age groups using vital sign parameters and risk indicators of deterioration.

Several studies have validated the PEWS, including one developed by Duncan et al. (2006), which found that it had an area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUROC) of 0.90, with 78% sensitivity and 95% specificity at a score of 5. These scores indicated that the PEWS was a valid and reliable tool. Additionally, a retrospective chart review of one hundred fifty children in a Texas children's hospital found the tool reliable and valid (Bell et al., 2013). A multicenter randomized controlled trial found that the PEWS model contributed to knowledge regarding the clinical deterioration for hospitalized children (Jensen et al., 2017; Parshuram., 2018). Furthermore, a 12-month observational study conducted on patients aged zero to twenty-one years admitted into the ED from an urban tertiary care children hospital found the PEWS had excellently captured nurse interrater reliability (Gold et al., 2014).

One limitation in the use of the PEWS was that there is no standardized model in practice leading to the lack of systematic implementation and use in pediatric settings (Gold et al., 2014). Most studies were retrospective cohort-case controlled studies, few were systematic reviews, and with very few randomized controlled studies. Similarly, some studies found that its results could not be generalized in all clinical settings (et al., 2015). Although the PEWS have limitations in many of the studies reviewed it was reliable at identifying the child at risk for deterioration (Rosman et al., 2019; McElroy et al., 2019; Bell et al., 2013).

According to Brown et al. (2019), the PEWS consisted of two components, the scoring tool, calculated at regular intervals during hospital admission and the response algorithm of interventions. and provider assessments based on the PEWS score. The PEWS incorporated

clinical information such as vital signs, neurologic status, work of breathing, and perfusion. Most studies which investigated the PEWS evaluated its usefulness in the inpatient setting.

Additionally, the PEWS scores were used to assess patients by applying an objective measure that helped alert staff to clinically deteriorating children (Lambert et al., 2017; Royal College of Physicians, 2017). This tracking consisted of periodic observation of physiological parameters, generation of a numeric score, and predetermined criteria for escalating urgent assistance with a clear framework for communication.

This PEWS quality improvement project will be guided by the five components of the PEWS tool kit (Appendix D), the PEWS scoring tool, PEWS escalation aid, normal vital signs parameter for pediatric patients by age, situational awareness, and the SBAR report. Each component is used in the assessment, decision making, escalation, and communication of the clinician when determining the health status of a deteriorating patient. *The PEWS Scoring Tool* was identified for pediatric patients at risk for clinical deterioration and is the well-established tool that provided an objected method to a pediatric patient deteriorating status. *Vital Signs* which include heart rate, respiration (breathing rate), blood pressure, and temperature. These are the clinical measurements that indicate the state of a patient's essential body functions. *The PEWS Escalation Aid* are interventions taken when risk was identified. If a patient's PEWS score is elevated and requires activation of the escalation process, the nurse takes the steps to escalate care to a higher level. *Situational Awareness* are factors that are present that can influence the escalation of care process. *The SBAR*, an acronym for Situation, Background, Assessment, Recommendation, is the method that can be used to facilitate prompt and appropriate communication between healthcare clinicians (McElroy et al., 2019) (Appendix D).

Assessment of Pediatric Patients

The Pediatric Nurse Scope and Standards of Practice delineated the core competencies for pediatric registered nurses used to guide practice (ANA et al., 2015). The pediatric nurse works with children ages newborn to nineteen, who suffer from various acute, chronic illnesses or congenital disorders requiring special healthcare needs. The Society of Pediatric Nurses (Mott et al., 2018) identified a core set of skills, attitudes, and behaviors that were essential for pediatric nurses to possess. Developing competencies and skills in the pediatric setting, nurses must repeatedly experience these various learning encounters. Young children have different respiratory and cardiovascular physiology compared to older children and adults and are at an increased risk of respiratory complications (Saikia & Mahanta, 2019). Because pediatric patients have a wide age range, the pediatric nurse's assessment skills must be precise for each child's clinical evaluation and needs. Equally important is the use of assessment tools such as the PEWS, which support a more thorough evaluation in the care of pediatric patients.

Pediatric Nursing Standards of Practice

Pediatric nursing has been a specialty since 1855 when the first children's hospital was founded in Philadelphia, Pennsylvania. The role of nurses during that time was to reduce childhood mortality primarily through research (National Association of Pediatric Nurse Practitioners [NAPNAP], 2015). Pediatric nursing as a specialty focuses on protecting, promoting, and optimizing children's health and abilities from birth through twenty-one years of age. The nursing scope of practice describes who, how and what with regards to the care of children. The scope of practice for pediatric nursing applies to all registered nurses (RNs) engaged in the care of children and their families regardless of clinical specialty, practice setting, or educational preparation. The practice further defined its standards of a competent nurse

through the nursing process. This process includes assessment, diagnosis, outcome identification, planning, and evaluation. The nursing process is the foundation for clinical decision-making and integration of the best research evidence available from clinical experts along with adherence to patient values (NAPNAP, 2015).

Clinical Competence of Nurses

Multiple factors determine the clinical competency of nurses who practice in acute care settings. The factors consist of experience, knowledge, expertise, and comfort level with their assessment and clinical judgment. Additionally, nurses require continuous professional development to maintain and increase their level of competence throughout their career pathway (Takase, 2013). Citing the work of Patricia Benner (Maisano, 2016), nurse competence falls into five developmental stages. The lowest level is novice, moving on to advanced proficient, expert, and world-class. The initial novice stage in the model involves an individual who has had no previous experience with a situation in which the individual's performance is guided by maxims consisting of visualizing the situation in its entirety. The proficient nurse has a holistic understanding of the situation which allows for in depth decision-making. The fifth level is expert, in which the individual can grasp the situation and understand what needs to be accomplished to solve a problem (Maisano, 2016). The assumption is that professionals grow by moving through these developmental stages; thereby, increasing their competency as they progress in their careers (Takase, 2013). Clinical competency is a set of attributes, personal characteristics, values, knowledge, and skills required to fulfill a nurse's professional development. The level of nursing competency directly affects the quality of care provided to patients. It is important to understand that competent and proficient nurses will not approach or solve problems later in their career in the same way they did as when they were novices. All

nurses need ongoing education and skills assessment to maintain and increase competency in their work (Takase, 2013).

Pediatric Nurses Core Competencies

Three national professional organizations, the American Nurses Association (ANA), the NAPNAP, and Society of Pediatric Nurses (SPN), work in partnership to publish the scope and standard of practice for pediatric nurses (NAPNAP, 2015). These organizations advance the interest and specialty of pediatric nursing (Mott et al., 2018). The SPN promotes pediatric nurses' careers and fosters numerous career enhancement opportunities. It provides global pediatric standards of care, and clinical practice guidelines that are integrated into health care. Education, professional organizations, networking, conferences, webinars, continuing education, certifications, facilitates the maintenance of a nurse's competency. These knowledge enhancement opportunities help to keep the nurse engaged and up to date in relevant practices.

Competencies are the key indicators which demonstrate a pediatric registered nurses' level of skills and knowledge in a specific area of practice. Standards should remain stable over time as they reflect the philosophical values of the profession. However, competencies must be revised to reflect current nursing practice (NAPNAP, 2015). There are core standards of nursing practice which include the competencies such as assessments that the pediatric registered nurse conduct using comprehensive data pertinent to the child's health and or situation. A competent nurse should be able to determine appropriate nursing diagnoses, which involve being able to analyze and synthesize the assessment data to a tangible need. The pediatric nurse must also be able to identify expected outcomes for a plan individualized to the child, family, or situation. The nurse must be able to develop a plan that prescribes strategies and alternatives to attain expected outcomes. Other aspects of competencies include coordination of care, health teaching and health

promotion, consultation, prescriptive authority, referrals, treatment, and therapies that regulated under federal laws, regulations, and evaluation. Finally, the pediatric nurse must be able to evaluate a patient's progress toward the attainment of outcomes. These help to ensure that the patient is being treated in a prescribed manner.

Communication and SBAR Report

An easy-to-use structured communication tool was originally designed and developed by the United States military for communication on nuclear submarines and is now widely used in healthcare settings such as Kaiser Permanente. This tool consists of standardized prompt questions divided into four sections: Situation, Background, Assessment, and Recommendation (SBAR). The four sections allow for information to be transferable between individuals caring for patients (ACT, 2018). The SBAR tool provided a framework for communication between the healthcare team members regarding a patient's condition (Lee, 2016). The acronym SBAR stands for the following:

S -Situation, which is a concise statement of the problem.

B -Background, which is pertinent brief information related to the Situation.

A -Assessment, which is the analysis and considerations of options. It describes what a person (found/thinks).

R -Recommendation, which is the action requested or recommended. It is what is needed to be done to ensure expedient care is provided.

Broader usage of the SBAR tool includes telephone communication from nurses to doctors in critical situations, general patient hand-off, and general team communication (Muller et al., 2018). Muller views the SBAR tool as a mechanism to increase handover quality and increase patient safety through effective communication. Stewart and Hand (2017) stated that

effective communication between nurses and doctors is essential to the patient's care. The Joint Commission (2013) defines hand-off as the real-time process of passing patient-specific information from one caregiver to another to ensure safe patient care continuity. The SBAR tool creates a common language for communication between nurses and doctors (Lee, 2016). Under a clear structure, SBAR calls for providing all relevant information, in an organized and logically format (Muller et al., 2018).

Furthermore, the SBAR enabled healthcare providers to prepare for the communication process by providing a structure for their conversation. Since the healthcare providers share the same mental model, their level of understanding and awareness of a situation is generally higher. The format helps to improve the clinician's confidence in providing an accurate report. There was efficiency and accuracy in the report because the SBAR template was the guide to reporting, and it was an effective method for an organized report (Stewart & Hand, 2017).

According to the Joint Commission (2015), communication errors have been among the top three leading root causes of reported sentinel events. Miscommunication between clinicians can increase the risk of incorrect execution of orders leading to dire consequences to the patient. Assessment findings communicated clearly and systematically lead to better reporting and better patient outcomes. As such, there are principles of effective communication that all providers (nurses and doctors) must adhere to when caring for patients. Excellent communication is essential to help a team function efficiently. Blom et al. (2015) stated that unclear and ineffective communication between healthcare professionals is a common underlying cause of patient injuries in healthcare (See Appendix D).

Safety

According to Raymond and Harrison (2014), effective communication, co-operation, and teamwork have been identified as key determinants of patient safety. The provision of safe care and improved care is a central part of the healthcare delivery system (Lachman, 2018). Likewise, pediatric providers should serve as advocates for best practices and policies to help mitigate the unique safety risks to children (Brady et al., 2013; Mueller et al., 2019). Clinicians should be identifying and supporting a culture of safety and leading efforts to eliminate avoidable harm in any setting where children are rendered medical care. According to the American Academy of Pediatrics (AAP; 2019), three key issues have been identified. Those three key issues are the significance of pediatric patient safety, the science behind the safety culture, and strategies to ensure patient safety.

Significance of Pediatric Patient Safety

In addition to understanding harm to children and the importance of protection, healthcare clinicians respond to assessment findings in real-time escalating safety concerns. (Mueller et al., 2019). The AAP has implemented patient safety guidelines that healthcare clinicians can incorporate into their practice. The significance of pediatric safety is due to the unique attributes of patient safety problems seen in three key domains: physical characteristics associated with weight-based medication dosing, developmental issues, as they pertain to the physical and mental age of the child, and issues regarding the minor's legal status when there is a lack of adult assistance in care or confidential health concerns (Mueller et al., 2019). Additionally, there are general layered safety concerns that impact pediatric patient care not detailed in this paper.

The Science Behind the Culture of Safety

Another aspect of concern was the culture of safety, which addressed human fallibility, the conditions under which people work, and build defenses to mitigate the effects. Similarly, Lachman (2018) echoed that healthcare delivery quality and safety rely on integrating many processes, all prone to potential failure. This indicated that for a culture of safety to be maintained, it must be the focus when caring for patients. Specifically, safety culture was fundamental for avoiding patient harm and emphasizes improving systems rather than blaming individual people (Mueller et al., 2019). This culture supports responding to errors or potential errors in with the expectation being to escalate or "stop the line" when safety was at risk. A culture of safety involved leaders and members understanding and acting based on a systems approach. As stated by Miller et al., (2019) no child should be harmed while trying to stay well, heal, or manage their chronic conditions via interactions with healthcare providers and systems.

Strategies to Ensure Patient Safety

Additional guidance on creating systems was in the Institute of Medicine (IOM) principles for designing safety systems in health care organizations. Methods used to assess and resolve patient safety issues incorporated the IOM's broad key safety-design concepts to improve reliability through redundancy, simplification, and standardization (Mueller et al., 2019). Evidence-based clinical practice guidelines can direct care decisions both toward wanted and away from unwanted actions, resulting in reduced opportunities for harm and improved outcomes (Mueller et al., 2019). Furthermore, leaders and clinicians who strive to improve patient safety need to appraise their organizations' safety culture and must advocate for the best means of implementing safety strategies. Other safety goals include recognizing a change in a patient's status or encouraging family involvement in the patient's care, by requiring a composite

of changes to the health care system so that providers and consumers expectations are honored. The role of technology has become significant, even though it cannot solve all the challenges to patient safety, it has helped to increase access to patient information. Likewise, many organizations have incorporated national patient safety goals as their guiding principles for practice. Thus, reducing pediatric patient harm attributable to medical care requires identifying and reporting errors and adverse events. Efforts should be made to disseminate best practices to prevent errors and cultivate a safety culture (Choi et al., 2014). It was only through the creation of a culture of safety that an assumption of personal responsibility for patient care outcomes can be accomplished. Healthcare providers must examine the areas of risk that interfere with pediatric patient safety. The providers must be able to deploy rigorous systems of evaluation to further reduce the risk of medical errors to children (Mueller et al., 2019).

The literature supports ongoing research in health care to address strategies for patient safety. Technology has brought many changes in patient safety. However, some issues are amenable to technology (Mueller et al., 2019). The Joint Commission (2019) has been instrumental in developing the basis of an objective process that can help organizations measure, assess, and improve performance. Each year the Joint Commission gathers information about emerging patient safety issues from experts and stakeholders and addresses them. Additional guidance on creating systems promoting a culture of safety was the IOM, which promoted principles for designing safety systems in a healthcare organization. Evidence-based clinical practice guidelines also direct nursing practices towards no harm and improved outcomes.

In conclusion, the literature has identified the PEWS as an objective, valid, and reliable tool to identify patients at risk of deterioration. A culture of safety is crucial in providing the best care to hospitalized children. Implementing evidence-based tools, assuring system readiness for

change with a delineated process such as the SBAR, and elevating the healthcare team competency are crucial elements in introducing improvement initiatives.

Methods

Design

The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project was to facilitate the implementation of Pediatric Early Warning Systems (PEWS) tool for use in the general pediatric unit. The aim of this project was threefold. The first was to assess current resources, barriers, strengths, and possible opportunities to use the tool within a local pediatric department. The second was to develop strategies focused on the systematic implementation and integration of the tool in the nurse and physician workflow. Finally, to develop an evaluation plan of the proposed change into nursing and physician workflow and ongoing practice.

Setting

The project setting was a pediatric unit with twenty-five inpatient beds and four observational outpatient beds within a 600-bed acute care hospital located in Southern California. It is one of the largest public hospitals in Los Angeles County. It is a premier academic teaching hospital for training health professionals across the country. The pediatric unit had twenty-five inpatient beds with four observational outpatient beds. The observational beds provided overflow space for the emergency room. The pediatric unit treats patients who are acutely ill; however, if they become critical, they are moved to the Pediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU). The children treated in the pediatric unit range in age from newborn to thirteen years old. Children who were fourteen or older were treated in the medical-surgical unit. There were six double rooms on the pediatric unit and each room can house two patients. One family member for each patient was permitted for overnight stays.

Stakeholders

The stakeholders of this quality improvement (QI) project were the nurses, doctors on the pediatric unit at the project facility, the director of pediatrics, manager of the project unit, the chief nursing officer (CNO), the chief executive officer (CEO) and staff. Stakeholders were vital to this PEWS tool's re-implementation, with the original work on this project started in 2016. The PDSA model was the framework used in the direction of this project. The primary aim was to see consistent utilization of the PEWS tool by nurses on the pediatric unit and both doctors and nurses using the PEWS tool to assess patients overall. The goal of the project was aimed to improve patient outcomes related to the pediatric patient's assessment and intervene with the appropriate intervention based on the established action plan. Although it is hard to measure this goal within this DNP project timeline, the aim of the team was to meet the goal.

Participants

The pediatric unit has thirty-six registered nurses, two hospitalists, thirteen physicians, one clinical nurse specialist, a nurse manager, and a nursing director. The nursing director, nurse manager, and two physician hospitalists were key stakeholders in implementing this project. The stakeholders have a vested interest in the project's outcome since their goal was to have consistent use of the PEWS across the unit.

Procedure

The re-introduction of this project had planned activities implemented in phases. The first phase was to assess the strength, aspirations, opportunities, and results within the pediatric department. The second phase involved an analysis of the findings identified in phase one. Based on the findings, strategies were developed that focused on the systematic re-implementation of

the PEWS tool utilization based on the SOAR analysis findings. In the final stage, monthly evaluation of nurses' utilization of the tool implementation was conducted.

Measures

The measures selected for data gathering and analysis were as followed:

- 1) Focus Groups: A Strength, Opportunity, Aspiration, and Results (SOAR) analysis was used to summarize key outcomes of each category using thematic analysis to develop recommendations for project implementation.
- 2) Demographic Data: The demographic data consisted of the number of nurses on the unit, their age ranges, years in nursing, years of experience in pediatric nursing.
- 3) Utilization tool: The pediatric unit adapted and re-implemented an established PEWS tool developed by the project facility's nursing education department. This tool and the Action Plan were the measures for pre-audits before re-education and post-audits after re-implementation of the tool and outcomes on the utilization of the PEWS tool. The tool was developed by a multidisciplinary group at the University Hospitals National Health Services Trust in the United Kingdom. Dr. Alan Monaghan led the project and was the original creator of the PEWS Scoring Tool.

A SOAR Analysis helped the organization focus on the current strengths and future vision for the benefits of developing strategic goals. The SOAR analysis is a strength based powerful tool guided by the appreciative inquiry model, which brings stakeholders together to recognize the organization's potential and create a shared vision of the future (Cole et al, 2016). Building on strengths requires less effort and resources than trying to correct weaknesses. A SOAR-based strategic thinking approach engages organizational members to frame organizational issues from

a solution-oriented perspective that is generative and focused on organizational strengths, opportunities, aspirations, and desired results to build a positive future (Cole et al., 2016).

The focus group was guided by four questions as they pertain to the implementation of the PEWS using a SOAR analysis (Appendix D). Focusing on the Strengths of the project was needed to determine the achievements, values, and positive outcomes that can result from the use of the PEWS. The Opportunities in the project helped to highlight the presenting concerns on the unit that addressed areas for improvement related to patient care and staff training. The Aspirations of the project were to improve the care provided to children in the pediatric unit. The Results of the project will help nurses improve the skills and practices they use to identify children at risk for deterioration through the implementation of the PEWS. Additionally, the tool's use will result in a safer and evidenced-based change to practice the aim of improving patient outcomes. For the project evaluation, ongoing monitoring, and an audit tool (Figure 9) were developed with the aim of assessing the frequency of completed assessments used weekly. The tool was developed in collaboration with the interdisciplinary team and was implemented in March 2021. (Appendix E)

Analysis

Several analyses were used depending on the nature of each measure. Focus groups conducted using the SOAR assessment. Analysis of data collected in the focus groups was analyzed using a thematic analysis approach of the team's narratives. Thematic analysis was conducted in collaboration with the unit educator and examined the group narratives, looking for patterns or themes within the data collected. These themes were categorized to formulate the result section, which entailed developing specific, measurable, attainable, and timed goals that informed the systematic implementation plan of the PEWS tool. Demographic data were

analyzed using descriptive statistics, which included range for participants gender, age, and years in practice.

The audit tool was used to assess the utilization of the PEWS from randomly selected charts of children admitted into the pediatric unit. Pre-PEWS documentation data audited four charts daily for seven days, and post-PEWS documentation data audited four charts daily for eight days. There were a total of sixty charts audited to assess nurse's utilization before and after PEWS implementation.

Daily pre- and post-PEWS scores (0 - 3) were collated and analyzed as mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM) for each day and displayed as line graphs. The daily means of pre- or post-PEWS scores were then reduced to a single data set to represent the average effect over time (seven days for pre-PEWS, eight days for post-PEWS), expressed as mean \pm SEM and displayed as bar graphs. Pre-PEWS seven-day data vs post-PEWS eight-day data were analyzed with an unpaired T-test to assess statistical significance; $p < 0.05$ was considered significant.

Utilization, intervention, and notification categories of the audit tool which were inputted as yes, or no were collated and computed as the number of yes entries per day (0 - 4). These data were then analyzed as daily mean \pm SEM and depicted as line graphs. Like the treatment of PEWS scores, these data were then reduced into single data sets to represent the average effect over time, expressed as mean \pm SEM and displayed as bar graphs. Unpaired T-tests were also done with these data sets to compare pre- vs post-PEWS; $p < 0.05$ was considered significant.

Ethical Considerations

The project proposal was submitted and approved by the International Review Boards (IRB) at California State University, Fullerton, and the project hospital as per the facility's policies regarding nursing quality improvement projects. Participants were informed via oral

explanation and written consent immediately before the educational presentation and consent was obtained. To maintain confidentiality, participants did not place any identifying information on the post-education surveys. For data collected from the patient charts, no patient identifiers were collected to maintain privacy.

Results

The aim of this project was threefold. The first was to assess the strengths, opportunities, aspirations, and results of using the PEWS at a local pediatric department at a Southern California hospital. The second was to develop strategies focused on the systematic implementation of the tool. And, finally, to assess nurses' utilization of the tool over a five-month period after re-implementation.

AIM 1- SOAR Analysis

The first AIM was to assess the strengths, opportunities, aspirations, and results of using the PEWS tool. To work on this AIM, a Focus Group was established consisting of six stakeholders from the project site and the project author. There were two doctors, the pediatrics director, the pediatric nurse manager, the unit educator, a resource personnel and the project author. The group met together via four Zoom meetings from November 2020, to February 2021. The focus group planned strategies to address the first aim pertaining to the Pediatric Early Warning Scores (PEWS). The other remaining meetings were also conducted via Zoom due to the COVID-19 pandemic and social distancing requirements. The group was guided by the Strength, Opportunities, Aspirations, and Results (SOAR) approach to addressing AIM -1. Since the PEWS tool was previously introduced in 2016 at the project site, the group also discussed the issues that were present during the initial introduction and what changes could be made to improve its usage during this re-implementation.

The subsequent Zoom meetings had fewer than half of the members in attendance. Due to the current pandemic, team members were re-assigned to new work locations or changed their schedules, thus they were not able to participate in the focus group meetings.

The findings of the focus were then collated and summarized using a systematic approach to analyzing the data and are captured in Figure 4.

Figure 4

SOAR Analysis- Matrix Findings

S		A	
<p>STRENGTH</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nursing staff highly motivated to use tool • Motivated nurses' team • Motivated doctors' team • Leadership support • Leadership commitment • Electronic Health Records build to accommodate the assessment 		<p>ASPIRATION</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement, assess, and care • Improve patient outcomes • Improve communication • Provide care based on evidence • 100% compliance with using the PEWS • Better provider satisfaction because of improved communication • Elevate knowledge, skills, attitude, critical thinking of nurses using the PEWS 	
O		R	
<p>OPPORTUNITIES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide better patient care • Create systematic policies that everyone can follow • Standardized patient care • Easy to navigate electronic charting flowsheet for PEWS • Standardized care and assessment • Improve communication between nurses and MD related to assessment • Reeducate the team • Build an inclusive team speaking the same language 		<p>RESULTS - SMART Goals:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop strategies for the tool implementation by March 23, 2021: education, reminder tool posted at bedside, and nurses' station. Create nurses "cheat sheet" or "Nurses Brain" • Complete re-education of all nurses by the end of March 2021 • Develop an online educational module on the use of the pew by April 2021. • Reeducate all nurses on the proper use of the PEWS by June 2021 	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foster better education opportunities for the staff 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Includes the PEWS online module in all new hires educational material starting June 2021 • Conduct annual competency validation • Charts indicate an 80% of assessments completed • Team debriefed after two months of day analysis
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In summary, the team's readiness to embark on a practice change was assessed. The focus group allowed different stakeholders' perspectives to be included and helped streamline the next steps for formulating a plan to move forward with the PEWS tool re-implementation. As the stakeholders pulled from their *strengths* of support for the tool and being highly motivated to re-implement this tool; they communicated the value they had placed in having the assessment tool in their healthcare practice. There were now new *opportunities* to build a more inclusive team in which nurses actively participated in team rounds, sharing their input, and clinical judgement in the care of patients. The *aspiration* was to see this tool used regularly by both the nurses and doctors and reengage the nurses and doctors in a commonality of care and assessment in which they speak from the same mental model. At the end of this process, the goal was to see *results* that indicated the project was successful, that it benefited the nurses and doctors in their assessment skills and built a more confident clinical team.

Considering the dynamics of the leadership and the stakeholders, the possibility of reengaging the doctors and nurses in this project seems favorable. With the stakeholders' vested interest, leadership support, and doctors receiving the PEWS education; the nurses likely followed through on utilizing the PEWS tool consistently, and the doctors developed more inclusive teamwork with the nurses by validating their assessment, knowledge, critical judgement, and input to the care of the pediatric population.

AIM II- Systematic Re-Implementation

The second aim was to develop strategies focused on the systematic re-implementation of the tool. AIM-II was developed from the finding identified in AIM-I by the focus group-SOAR analysis findings and thoroughly constructed for the next step in the process. To develop a systematic re-implementation of the tool, several activities were undertaken. Starting from the first week in December, the project author conducted several weekly visits to the project facility to gather demographic data from the nurses and doctors and used the time for informal talks about the PEWS. The project author met with the Information Technology (IT) manager. The IT manager showed the project author how to navigate the Cerner/Orchid patient chart and described some of the technical concerns. This tutorial was beneficial in gaining a better understanding of the electronic charting system at the project site. Based on the findings in AIM-1, it was important to re-engage the nurses with re-education, discuss the benefits of a collegial team relationship with the doctors and share the rationale of adding the PEWS tool to their assessment. Nurses knew they had a significant role to play, not only in reporting clinical findings, but sharing their clinical assessment knowledge, judgement, and skills in their reports.

Demographic Survey Data for Nurses and Doctors

A demographic survey (Table 1) was conducted before the doctors' and nurses' PEWS re-education on the pediatric unit was completed. The information included age, gender, years in practice, years in pediatric specialty, and title. Thirty-six nurses completed the survey, and fifteen doctors did the same. The data gathered showed that thirteen of these nurses had fewer than five years of experience in the profession. This finding indicated that a third of the staff are getting this PEWS education for the first time, and that is substantial.

Table 1*Demographic Information of Participants*

Categories	N
Nurses	36
Doctors	15
Male	11
Female	40
Nurses' age range	
20-30	2
31-40	9
41-50	10
51 & above	15
Doctors' age range	
20-30	12
31-40	3
41-50	0
51 & above	0
Years in practice and specialty nurses	
0-5	13
6-10	4
11-15	3
16-20	4
21-25	3
26-30	9
31 & above	0
Years in practice and specialty doctors	
0-5	0
6-10	15
11 & above	0

Re-education of the PEWS

The second goal identified was focused on re-educating the nurses. The first group who completed the education consisted of nurses from both day and night shifts. The leadership decided that a more convenient way to educate the nurses was to provide a voice-over PowerPoint. This was provided for nurses who missed the in-person education rollout. This would allow the nurses to do a self-learning education review to be compliant with the PEWS education requirement. It also serves as an available resource for nurses who would like to

review the education again independently. Case studies were shared with the group during these education sessions to reinforce learning. A few nurses were unable to be the in-person education, so they reviewed the PowerPoint and the case studies. Nurses were given opportunities to ask questions about the education, the PEWS tool, and their input and perspectives were invaluable information during these education sessions.

The PEWS education would be useful for new staff who were not at the facility during a previous education of the PEWS tool in 2016. Additionally, nurses who had the education previously needed re-education for the purpose of being current with the tool. Over four weeks starting from the second week of February to the second week of March, the 25-minute PowerPoint education presentation was conducted by the project author with the pediatric nurses. Other aids to the re-education were provided for the nurses were lanyards with quick access to PEWS information, nurses' brain cheat sheet and a flashlight. The groundwork of the education on PEWS was based on the work done by the nursing department, medical doctors, and the nurse educator at the project facility. The re-education was completed, and the next step is utilization of the PEWS tool by the nurses.

Preparing the Unit

An additional part of the re-implementation was preparing the environment to support this assessment tool. The PEWS Tool and Action Plan were laminated and placed in the areas where nurses and doctors chart and discuss patient's health status. The information was within sight and served as a visible reminder to clinicians to use the tool in their assessment, documentation, and communication. This assessment tool information was used in their shift-to-shift reports, charge nurses' huddles, doctor/patient rounds and when patient care was escalated to another level.

Re-Implementation

Re-implementation of the tool officially started March 23, 2021. The project author was on the unit to support the nurses with any questions or concerns they had. Most of the nurses indicated that they were familiar with the tool, how to navigate the electronic system and were not in need of additional support. The timeline for the re-implementation of the PEWS tool was much later than originally planned by the project author, due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Incidentally, many of the nurses had already started to document in the PEWS, prior to implementation of the project. The expectation was for nurses to include the PEWS assessment in their documentation and all their shift-to-shift reports, charge nurse' huddles, and team rounds with the doctors.

AIM III - Assess Nurses' Utilization of the Tool after Implementation.

The utilization of the PEWS tool was the essential phase of the project. This phase established the tool's use, consistency in documentation, and practicality to the nurses. During this phase, the stakeholders and nurse leaders must continue to maintain their support for the project and gather feedback on how well the nurses were adjusting to the PEWS tool. Prior to implementation, a baseline chart audit was conducted over a seven-day period. After the implementation, ongoing chart audits were conducted to determine the tool's utilization by the project author and the unit Charge Nurses (CN). The focus of these audits was to monitor its usage, interventions based on PEWS Action Plan. The audits revealed to whom the information was communicated, what measures were implemented for patient escalation, how timely the responses were, and the correct response used in each case.

PEWS Data Audits Collated

After the nurse education was completed and implementation of the tool was done March 23, 2021, random chart audits were conducted for the week of pre-PEWS implementation, March 2-9, 2021, and post-PEWS implementation, March 23-30, 2021. This data was collated and analyzed. Four patients' PEWS documentation was collated each day for seven days pre-implementation and four patients' chart documentation was collated for eight days post-PEWS. The education showed significant PEWS utilization post-implementation.

Audit tool questions.

1. Was the PEWS tool utilized routinely on the shift? (routine means documentation with vital signs two to three times a shift)? Yes/No.
2. Was a PEWS numerical score calculated and assigned to the patient's chart? (Score 0 – 3)
3. Was there an intervention for PEWS score greater than three? Yes/No.
4. Was there notification to the provider for a patient's score greater than three? Yes/No.

The form used in the audit is reproduced in Appendix F. The raw scores and responses collected from the four patients were collated and reported in Appendix G, along with descriptive statistics.

Graphical representation of the analyzed data is shown in Figures 5, 6, 7.

Figure 5*Daily Pre- and Post-Scores and Responses to PEWS Education*

Note. Seven days of pre- and eight days of post-responses to PEWS education. Panel A shows PEWS scores. Panel B, C and D depict # of YES responses in up to four patients/day. Data on questions of utilization, intervention and notification are illustrated in Panels B, C and D, respectively.

Figure 5 summarizes the daily responses to the audit for both pre- and post-PEWS education. Panel A shows the average PEWS scores of up to four patients each day for over seven days during the pre-phase and over eight days during the post-phase. Scores ranged from 0 to 1 during the pre-phase and 0 – 0.75 during the post-phase. Panel B illustrates the daily responses for utilization of the PEWS tool, both pre- and post-PEWS education. Data are expressed as the average of the number of YES responses from up to four patients per day. The average ranged from 1 to 2 over seven days for pre- and 3 to 4 for post-PEWS education. Panel C depicts the daily average responses for the intervention question. The number of YES responses from up to four patients per day in the pre- phase over seven days was 0. For the post-

phase, the number of YES responses over eight days was also 0, except for days three and eight, where the responses were 3 and 1, respectively. Panel D shows the responses to the question on notification. Prior to PEWS education, the pre-phase, the number of YES responses in up to four patients per day was 0 over seven days. It was also 0 for the post- phase except for day eight where the response was 2.

Figure 6

Daily PEWS Scores Averaged over Eight Days

Note. There was no significant difference between pre- and post-PEWS scores. N.S. = Not significant.

Figure 6 shows the mean and standard error of the mean (SEM) of seven days of pre-PEWS scores and eight days of post-PEWS scores. Pre- and Post-PEWS scores were 0.4 ± 0.2 and 0.4 ± 0.1 , respectively; $p = 0.84$, utilizing an unpaired T-test.

Figure 7

Daily Responses Averaged Over Eight Days for Utilization, Intervention and Notification

Note. The daily number of YES responses averaged over 8 days was statistically significantly different between pre- and post-PEWS for utilization: * $p < 0.0001$, unpaired T-test. There was no statistical difference between pre- and post-PEWS for intervention nor notification. N.S. = Not significant.

Figure 7 illustrates the mean and SEM of the number of YES responses of seven days of pre- and eight days of post-PEWS for the following questions: utilization (Q2), intervention (Q3) and notification (Q4). Pre- and post-PEWS number of YES responses for utilization were 1.6 ± 0.2 and 3.6 ± 0.2 , respectively; * $p = 0.0000042$, unpaired T-test. Pre- and post-PEWS number of YES for intervention were 0 ± 0 and 0.5 ± 0.4 , respectively; $p = 0.24$. Pre- and post-PEWS number of YES for notification were 0 ± 0 and 0.3 ± 0.3 , respectively; $p = 0.27$.

PEWS Documentation

Date	Time	Behavior/Score	Cardiovascular/Score	Respiratory/Score	Total Score	Action Taken

Vitals

Date	Time	HR	RR	B/P	SpO2	O2 therapy	FiO2	Temp
Date	Time	HR	RR	B/P	SpO2	O2 therapy	FiO2	Temp

PAIN SCALE – Numeric, Wong-Baker, FLACC

Date	Time	Brief Description if applicable	Score

Provider Notification

Date	Time	Brief Details

Note. Adapted by LAC+USC, 2021.

Discussion

This quality improvement (QI) project was aimed to re-implement the PEWS assessment tool into the workflow of nurses at a pediatric unit in a Southern California hospital. In the consideration of re-implementing the PEWS tool at the project site, stakeholders and the nursing leadership had to weigh in on why this tool was beneficial to be used in the care of children at their facility.

The project author has been working with the project site leaders and stakeholder since November 2020, to help operationalize the PEWS project. The focus group was formed to work out the process from planning to implementation. The focus group was extremely beneficial launching the project. The two doctors who were part of the foundational work on the PEWS in 2016 had the history of their work and their perspectives to share and contribute to the focus group. Their knowledge and insights were invaluable to the group. The nurse educator brought the teaching elements developed by her and the medical team. The pediatric unit manager permitted the project author to make frequent visits to the facility to conduct demographic information gathering from the doctors and nurses and the re-education of the PEWS. This team outlined the desired results based on the internal knowledge of the system, the history of the previous intervention implementation attempts, knowledge of the available strengths and resources, while allowing the project author to help co-create the change they aspired to accomplish. This is a value added when using a strategic change modality that embraces team strengths and channels their aspiration to identify and works on achieving opportunities for better evidence-based practices.

In mid-March 2021, the nursing staff's education was completed, and many nurses have started unofficial usage of the PEWS tool. The next step in the project is the official rollout of

the PEWS use by nurses in the pediatric unit. One cautionary note, the word re-implementation is used in this DNP project to make known that this project had originally begun almost five years ago. Due to poor utilization of the tool, it became outmoded over time. This time the rollout education focused on why the tool is beneficial for nurses to use and used a systematic implementation method that included all stakeholders (nurses, physicians, EHR specialist, unit educator, and unit leadership team).

The focus group was formed including stakeholders, nurse leaders, doctors, a nurse educator, a staff personnel and the project author. Seven persons made up the original group, which was launched in November 2020. During Zoom meetings discussions on the plans for the utilization of the PEWS tool, concerns about the electronic charting system and how to move forward with the plan were discussed. These meetings, although scheduled for weekly updates, were not sustainable with the full group each time. Due to the pandemic, some members had job reassignments that made attending these meetings sessions difficult on any regular basis.

The group's particular goal was to re-implement the PEWS on the pediatric unit. Each member of the team indicated that they were excited that this quality improvement project was being considered once again for re-implementation. Each member was eager to contribute their input to the project. The planning phase was comprehensive as the group considered all the things that they had already achieved with previous work done and what they hope to accomplish at this time. One strength of the team was they all had worked together for many years and were comfortable sharing their perspectives. The project author had limited insight of the organization and the work they had done on PEWS over the years, so she presented her perspective based on what she knew about the benefit of the PEWS tool.

During the third week in February, one of the lead doctors had an idea for creating a second quality improvement (QI) project, one targeting the nurses and one targeting the doctors. She introduced a medical intern to the team and tasked him with the responsibility of working on the second QI project for the doctors while the project author solely focused on the nurses. This specifically targeted approach was helpful to introduce the project to all clinicians in less time. Doctors who never had PEWS education can benefit from their doctor project leader who is accessible and had participated in a similar project at another hospital.

One benefit of coming into a project with stakeholders who already have a committed interest in the project is the enthusiasm they bring to the table but sometimes strongly opinionated. One of the doctors and a stakeholder has a long history with the project and was modifying the original work on the PEWS for several months. Her vested interest was to see the successful implementation of the project. The Chief Nursing Officer (CNO) and the Chief Medical Resident were all stakeholders in the project. Using the SOAR analysis approach, the team commitment became evident over time. According to Cole et al., (2016) a collaborative team is more likely successful when working together cohesively. Stakeholders who value and support a project, not only for the result that they want to achieve but for the contribution of each member, bring to the group value in everyone's input, and more likely come up with a more comprehensive and strategic plan for the project.

What changes can we make that will result in an improvement? The PDSA model was most appropriate for guiding change in healthcare practices as it allowed for the testing of a small change, provided an opportunity for refinement at each stage, and has the potential to reveal additional areas of improvement (Bittle et al., 2016). The method is widely accepted for

healthcare improvement and used in the undertaking of quality improvement projects (Taylor et al., 2014).

Several Plan-Do Study-Act (PDSA) cycles were utilized in each step of the project which helped in making small changes and allowing the team to see results that were pointing to the direction of the tool adoption. In doing this QI project there were several PDSA cycles before the project can reach the final adaptation phase. The PDSA cycles in this project started with the formation of the focus group, where plans and strategies were developed, then working with the department educator to see how best to re-educate the nurses, then preparing the nurses and the unit for re-implementation of the PEWS tool. These PDSA iterative aspect cycles allows for testing and adapting one intervention at a time.

When considering the treatment of children, the utmost of care must be made available, since children cannot fully communicate for themselves as it pertains to their health status or illnesses. The healthcare environment must incorporate systems and practices that contributes to efficiency, competence, and good outcomes. These can be achieved when an organization is willing to invest in best evidence practice and provide their healthcare clinicians with equipment and support that facilitates good job performance.

Implications for Practice

It is important that inter-professional teams and nurse leaders look to Evidence-Based Practice (EBP) when considering best strategies for implementing a new practice change. EBP is based on research findings that are proven to enhance clinical practice, patient outcomes and produce a higher quality of care. Studies have indicated that the PEWS is an efficient, quick, and easy method for providing a clinical evaluation. According to McElroy et al. (2019), the PEWS scoring tool helps to improve the recognition of early signs of deterioration among pediatric

patients. The PEWS is also a well-established assessment tool. According to Gold et al. (2014) the tool is recognized for its practicality and reliability nationally and internationally.

Over the months with this project at the facility, the nurses' familiarity and usage of the PEWS tool were more evident. Many of them indicated that they chart using the PEWS tool but do not share their assessment information during shift reports, huddles, or rounds with doctors. With the implementation of the PEWS, documentation using this tool was official for the nurses on the pediatric unit from the fourth week of March. Nurses were required to chart their PEWS assessment and report the scores in their shift reports. The full utilization of the tool will be realized when the doctors have completed their PEWS education and can engage in more meaningful communication with nurses on the unit. Doctors and nurses will then have a shared information report that both can use to understand the clinical status and trends of patients in their care. The results from this study found a statistically significant utilization of the PEWS tool post-education by nurses. We can surmise that the tool was more meaningful to their documentation or that they found it to be a practical help in their clinical assessment. It would be pertinent to continue an effective workflow by maintaining a systematic way of using these assessment findings. This may include communication among the doctors and nurses and in all aspects of reporting, escalating to a higher level of care or being transferred to a different area.

Limitations

The project implementation encountered several setbacks and delays due to the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic. As a result, The PEWS project was not started on the original timeline. The pandemic played an integral part in most of the delays. The project author had to get permission to be at the project site when it was feasible to staffing situations or the business of the unit and abide by the changes made by leadership at the project site as to when she can be

there on campus. Most focus group sessions had fewer than the full team due to the demands of those working at the project site and their changing schedules. The project author was involved with the project's official implementation but had limited time left to be at the facility to support the nurses and leadership through the process. Moreover, hearing directly from the nurses and doctors giving their feedback on the process would have given insight into their use of the PEWS tool. Due to her volunteer status at the facility, the project author did not have the opportunity to be immersed in the project's daily aspects.

Recommendations

An important component of a practice changes when adapted, it must be maintained.

Some recommendations that must be considered for this project are the following:

- Nurse educators to work on a policy for the PEWS.
- Review standard of care to assure PEWS is included in patient assessment.
- Include yearly competency evaluation for pediatric nurses.
- Educate all nurses to the use of the PEWS tool.
- Include PEWS in new hires education.
- Require PEWS education for float pool nurses.

Conclusion

The PEWS has been validated as a reliable and effective tool in the assessment of children. Each healthcare facility that wants to provide the best care should implement this tool. Nurses' confidence and competence in the care of children can only increase as they get comfortable validating their clinical judgment with a tool that supports their findings. A bedside nurse also has the advantage of observing and assessing the status of a child for many continuous hours and is better able to see the changes in a child's condition. Since the PEWS tool has been available for some time now and used widely, it can only help to enhance patient care and patient's outcomes.

The leadership and stakeholders at the project site have fully embraced this tool implementation and intend to be supportive in its maintenance. They will incorporate the recommendations suggested making sure the project is fully realized on the pediatric unit and hopefully expand beyond this unit. A post-PEWS audit of the tool has shown promising signs of increased utilization which was the main goal. Ongoing chart audits will continue to tell the story of utilizing the PEWS tool on the pediatric over the next five months.

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APPENDIX A

Cumulative Index of Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL) Database Search

Table A*Cumulative Index of Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL) Database Search*

Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
PEWS & Pediatric early warning signs	Peer Reviewed, English language, Publish Date: 2014-2020	205	119	86	11
Nurse competency	Peer Reviewed, English language Publish Date: 2014-2020	24	18	6	6
Trigger Tool pediatrics	Peer Reviewed, English language Publish Date: 2014-2020	88	83	5	5
Vital signs and deterioration	Peer Reviewed, English language Publish Date: 2014-2020	1779	1774	5	5
Nurse Knowledge	Peer Reviewed, English language Publish Date: 2014-2020	1423	1417	6	6
Monitor's pediatrics	Peer Reviewed, English Publish Date: 2014-2020	1847	1835	12	12
Technology pediatrics	Peer Review, English Publish Date: 2014-2020	4721	4714	7	7

Note. Articles excluded were based on title and relevance to project topic.

APPENDIX B

PubMed Database Search

Table B*PubMed Database Search*

Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
PEWS & Pediatric early warning signs	Peer Reviewed, English language, Publish Date: 2014-2020	603	581	22	11
Nurse competency	Peer Reviewed, English language Publish Date: 2014-2020	215	206	9	4
Trigger Tool pediatrics	Peer Reviewed, English language Publish Date: 2014-2020	10	6	4	2
Vital signs and deterioration	Peer Reviewed, English language Publish Date: 2014-2020	17	10	7	2
Nurse Knowledge	Peer Reviewed, English language Publish Date: 2014-2020	8	5	3	2
Monitors' pediatrics	Peer Reviewed, English language Publish Date: 2014-2020	0	0	0	0
Technology pediatrics	Peer Reviewed, English language Publish Date: 2014-2020	2	0	2	2

Note. Articles excluded were based on title and relevance to project topic.

APPENDIX C

Science Direct Database Search

Table C*Science Direct Database Search*

Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
PEWS & Pediatric early warning signs	Peer Reviewed, English language, Publish Date: 20142020	205	119	86	11
Nurse competency	Peer Reviewed, English language	24	18	6	0
Trigger Tool pediatrics	Peer Reviewed, English language, Publish Date: 20142020	4	3	1	1
Nurse Knowledge	Peer Reviewed, English language, Publish Date: 20142020	3	3	0	0
Monitors' pediatrics	Peer Reviewed, English language, Publish Date: 20142020	8	7	1	1

Note. Articles excluded were based on title and relevance to project topic. This review is focused on the pediatrics early warning system scoring tool (PEWS); this tool is used for pediatric assessment to predict objective determination of a patient's deterioration. The PEWS assess three categories of a patient's clinical condition, behavior, cardiovascular, and respiratory. In addition, a review of nurses' clinical competence, communication, and safety studies will be reviewed.

APPENDIX D

PEWS Five Parts Tool Kit

- SBAR Report Sheet
- PEWS Scoring Tool
- PEWS Escalation Aid for Inpatient and Emergency Department Settings
- Normal Vital Signs for Pediatric Patients
- Situational Awareness

SBAR Report Sheet

S	<p>Situation: What is the situation you are calling about?</p> <p>I am calling about – (patient name and location) The patient code status is (code status, if known) The problem I am calling about is _____ I am afraid this child is having some difficulties.</p> <p>I have just assessed the child personally: Vital signs are BP _____ Pulse _____ Temperature _____ Sats _____ I am concerned about the (share concerns about the patient) Blood Pressure because it is _____ Pulse because it is less than _____ or over _____ Respiration because it is less than _____ or over _____ Temperature because it is less than _____ or over _____ PEWS score is _____</p>
B	<p>Background Pertinent information & Relevant History</p> <p>The child's mental status is: Describe (alert, & oriented to person, place, and time) Agitated Inconsolable Irritable Restless Sleepy</p>
A	<p>Assessment: What do you think the problem is?</p> <p>This is what I think the problem is: (say what you think is the problem) The problem seems to be (respiratory, neurological, physical, pain, etc.) I am not sure what the problem is, but the child is (crying excessively, sleeping continuously, grimacing often, etc.) The child's condition seems to be getting worse, we need to do something</p>

R	Recommendation: What do you want to happen?
	I suggest or request that you (say what you would like to see done)
	Transfer the patient to the PICU.
	Come see the child at this time.
	Talk to the child's family about code status.
	Ask the on-call pediatric resident to see the patient now.
	Ask the (Peds specialist) to see the patient now.
	Are any test needed:
	Do you need any tests, BMP, CBC, CXR, EKG or Others?
	If change in treatment is ordered, (then ask):
How often do you want vital sign?	
How long do you expect this problem to last?	
If the child's is not improving, when would you want us to call you?	

Note. This form consists of standardized prompt questions in four sections, Situation-Background-Assessment-Recommendation (SBAR), that enables information to be transferred accurately between individuals (ACT, 2018).

PEWS Scoring Tool

Table 1.1	0	1	2	3	Score
Cardiovascular	Pink or capillary refill 1-2 seconds	Pale or capillary refill 3 seconds	Grey or capillary refill 4 seconds. Tachycardia 20 above normal rate	Grey and mottled or capillary refill ≥ 5 seconds Tachycardia about 30 seconds above normal rate or bradycardia	
Respiratory	Within established baseline. No retraction Room air	≥ 10 above established baseline Mild contractions Up to 2L/min or 30%	≥ 20 above established baseline. Moderate contraction up to 4L/min or 40%	≥ 30 above established baseline. Severe contraction Grunting Up to 4L/min or 50%	
Behavior	Playing/Appropriate or sleep	Irritable but consolable	Irritable and inconsolable Restless or pain	Lethargic or confused. Reduced response to voice or pain	
Additional 2 pts for.					
nebulizers use every 15 minutes					
persistent vomiting after surgery					
					Total

Table 1.2 Retraction Severity		
Mild	Moderate	Severe
Subcostal or Substernal	Intercostal or Supraclavicular	Suprasternal or Sternal

Note. Why to Use The PEWS: It provides an objective measurement for patients who "look sick." It can help the less experienced clinician get a sense of which patients may need escalation of care. It can be used in pediatric patients of all ages.

When to Use: Utilize this PEWS tool when pediatric patients are admitted to the hospital.

Next Steps: Consider escalation of care in patients with high PEWS (≥ 3), including consulting with senior staff, increasing frequency of vital signs measurements, and clinical assessments, and/or consultation to an intensive care unit. (Kwon, 2018)

PEWS Escalation Aid for Inpatient and Emergency Department Settings

Pediatric Early Warning System Score		0-1	2	3	4	5-13
	Notify		Consider reviewing patient with a more experienced healthcare provider	*For a score of "3" in any one category consider higher escalation As per PEWS Score 2	& or score increased by 2 after interventions As per PEWS Score 2 AND notify most responsible physician (MRP) or Physician delegate Based on rate of deterioration, consider pediatrician consult	Or score "3" in one category MRP to assess patient immediately (& pediatrician if available) If MRP unable to attend, call for STAT physician review. Appropriate senior review
	Plan				MRP or delegate communicate a plan of care to mitigate contributing factors of deterioration. Communicate plan of care or	As per PEWS Score 4

					the patient and /or family	
Assessment	Continue assessment, monitoring, and documentation as per orders & routine protocols	As per PEWS Score 1	Increase frequency of assessments & documentation as per plan from consultation with more experienced healthcare provider	Increase frequency of assessments & documentation as per plan		As per PEWS Score 4
Resources			Escalate if further consultation required or if resources do not allow for safe monitoring and care	Resources' adequacy of resources and make changes as needed: RN to patient ratio Location: ensure appropriate level of skill, equipment, medication, and resources available Consider internal or external consult or trans to higher level of care		As per PEWS Score 4
Situational Awareness	<p>If patient is assessed with one or more of the following situational awareness factors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Parent concern ▪ Sitter patient → Follow PEWS Score 2 action ▪ Unusual therapy ▪ Breakdown in communication 					

Note. The Escalation aid is an adaptation from Cook Children’s Medical Center, helps to support clinical decision making following an assessment. Recommended mitigation actions, such as notification, reassessment, and consultation, in many cases it corresponds to the PEWS score and the situational awareness factors. (McElroy et al., 2019)

Normal Vital Signs Parameters of Pediatric Patients by Age

Age Group	Heart Rate	Respirations	Systolic BP
Preterm	120-180	50-70	40-60
Newborn (0 to 1 Month)	100-160	35-55	50-70
Infant (1 to 12 Months)	80-140	30-40	70-100
Toddler (1 to 3 Years)	80-130	20-30	70-110
Preschool Age (6 to 12 Years)	80-110	20-30	80-110
School Age (6 to 12 Years)	70-100	18-24	80-120
Adolescents (12+ Years)	60-90	14-22	100-120

Note. A guide to the parameters of pediatric patient normal vital signs age group categories (McElroy et al., 2019).

Situational Awareness

Situational Awareness

There are five factors that would prompt the identification of a pediatric patient as being at increased risk:

Patient/Family/Caregiver Concern

	<p>A concern that has the potential to impact immediate patient safety</p>	<p>Family states the patient is worsening or not behaving as they normally would.</p>
	<p style="text-align: center;">“Sitter” Patient</p> <p>A patient that you identify as requiring increased observations for example</p>	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unexpected responses to treatments • Child different from “normal” • Aggressive patient 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Certified” patient • Over/under hydration • “Gut” feeling
	<p style="text-align: center;">Communication Breakdown</p> <p>Describe clinical situations when there is lack of clarity about:</p>	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Treatment • Plans Responsibilities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conversation outcomes • Language barriers
	<p style="text-align: center;">Unusual Therapy</p> <p>Includes staff unfamiliar with unit or department, therapy, or process. For example,</p>	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Float nurses or break coverage. • High risks infusion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New medication or protocol for patient or nurse
<p style="text-align: center;">P.E.W.S.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Pediatric Early Warning System Score 2 or Higher</p>	
	<p>Relevant patient assessment findings are summated into a score that can be used to identify patient physical deterioration early, so to optimize chances for intervention. These include:</p>	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Cardiovascular, respiratory, and behavioral data• Persistent vomiting following surgery.• Use of bronchodilators <p>A score of 2 or higher should trigger increased awareness</p>
--	---

Note. Situational Awareness component is an adaptation from the Cincinnati Situational model, this awareness factor is associated with the risk of pediatric clinical deterioration. There are five risk factors: patient/family/caregiver concern, patient assigned a sitter, communication breakdown, unusual therapy, and PEWS Score of two or higher (McElroy et al., 2019).

APPENDIX E

Demographic Survey Questionnaire

Pediatric Early Warning Score (PEWS) Quality Improvement Project
IRB # HRS-20-21-60

You are invited to participate in a quality improvement (QI) project entitled '*Pediatrics Early Warning Scores (PEWS) A Quality Improvement Project on a Pediatric Unit*' being conducted by Shelley Burke, Principal Investigator (PI), at LAC+USC Medical Center. This QI project will not include any personal identification, not even the Principal Investigator (PI) will be able to associate your responses to any questions with your identity. Your participation is voluntary. You must be at least 18 years of age to participate in this (QI) project. Your completion of this participation and demographic consent serves as your voluntary agreement to participate in this QI project and your certification that you 18 or older. Please do not write your name or put any other identifying information on the response sheet.

Participants:

Would you like to participate in this Quality Improvement Project?

Please indicate with a **check mark** to either yes or no.

Yes _____

No _____

PARTICIPANTS DEMOGRAPHIC QUESTIONS

Please answer the following questions

1. Role: RN _____ MD _____ Hospitalist _____ Educator _____ Director _____
Manager _____ CNS _____
2. Years in practice _____
3. Years in pediatric specialty _____
4. Gender (F) or (M) _____
5. Age range: 20-25 ___ 26-30 ___ 31-35 ___ 36-40 ___ 41-45 ___ 46-50 ___ 51-55 ___ 56 & above ___

Thank you.

QI Project Contact: Shelley Burke

California State University Fullerton (CSUF)

Note. Above is a demographic survey completed by both nurses and doctors on the pediatric unit. The information gives the # of nurses and doctors on the pediatric unit, years in practice, years in pediatric specialty and their age ranges.

APPENDIX F

Data Collection Audit Sheet

Audit sheet- Data to be collected for each patient (4 patients daily)
For one-week pre-PEWS implementation (March 2-9)
For one week post PEWS implementation (March 23 – 30)

- PEWS completion= charts showing pews scores with vital signs every four hours or minimum twice on the shift. **Yes or no**
- PEWS score = # total assigned by nurse
- Was an “ACTION PLAN” implemented for high scoring PEWS Yes or no
- Was the physician notified for scores greater than 3? Yes or no

How to document the information from each patient’s chart

Patients	Utilization		PEWS Score	Intervention		Notification	
	Yes	No		Yes	No	Yes	No
	PEWS documentation (routine = with 4-hour vital signs or a least twice in a 12-hour shift)			Action plan implemented for PEWS score greater than 3 in one domain or many domains		Provider Notification completed for patients with high PEWS scores or greater than 3	
1.							
2.							
3.							
4.							

Note. A sample copy of the sheet used to obtain patients raw PEWS data

APPENDIX G

Raw Patient Data and Summary Data of Pre-Post PEWS

Raw Data																
Question #	Patient #	PRE							POST							
		Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 4	Day 5	Day 6	Day 7	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 4	Day 5	Day 6	Day 7	Day 8
Q1	1	1		0		0	1	0	0	0		0	0	1	0	0
	2	1	1		0		1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0
	3	1		0		0		0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
	4			0	0				1	0	1	1	0		0	3
Q2	1	Y		Y		Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
	2	Y	Y		N		Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
	3	N		N		Y		Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
	4			N	Y				N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Q3	1	N		N		N	N	N	N	N		N	N	N	N	N
	2	N	N		N		N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N
	3	N		N		N		N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N
	4			N	N				N	N	Y	N	N		N	Y
Q4	1	N		N		N	N	N	N	N		N	N	N	N	Y
	2	N	N		N		N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
	3	N		N		N		N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
	4			N	N				N	N	N	N	N		N	Y
Patients Daily Summary (N=4)																
Question #	Statistics	PRE							POST							
		Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 4	Day 5	Day 6	Day 7	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 4	Day 5	Day 6	Day 7	Day 8
Q1	Mean	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1
Q2	# of Y	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	3	4	3	4	4	3	4	4
Q3	# of Y	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	1
Q4	# of Y	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
8 Day Summary (n=4)																
Question #	PRE (Days 1 - 7)				POST (Days 1 - 8)				Question Code							
	Mean	SD	SEM		Mean	SD	SEM		1. PEWS Score (0-3)	2. Utilization of PEWS (Y/N)	3. Intervention Action Plan (Y/N)	4. Notification of MD (Y/N)				
Q1	0.4	0.5	0.2		0.4	0.3	0.1									
Q2	1.6	0.5	0.2		3.6	0.5	0.2									
Q3	0.0	0.0	0.0		0.5	1.1	0.4									
Q4	0.0	0.0	0.0		0.3	0.7	0.3									

Note. This table shows the raw data collected on patients' pre-PEWS documentation for seven days on up to four patients daily and the post-PEWS documentation for eight days for up to four patients daily. A pre-post summary of the data represents the statistical findings.

APPENDIX H

Pediatric ‘Nurses Brain’ with PEWS

Date:		Room#
Dx		Allergies: Code:
Hx		IV
NEURO		Tests
CV		Skin
Resp		Meds
GI	GU	Labs
PEWS Score =	PEWS Action Plan:	Hospital Course:
Vital Signs:		Diet:
Notes:		Activity:

Note. Most nurses like to have handy a sheet of paper with the information of their patient for a convenient referral for what the need to do for each of their patient. This nurse’s “Brain” was created with an area for the PEWS Score and PEWS Action for the nurses at the project site.

APPENDIX I

PEWS Quick Referral Lanyard

Front

Back

Note. Quick referral lanyards were made and given to nurses to have a quick referral to the PEWS scoring information. The front shows the parameter of the tool. The back shows what action plan is needed based on the patient's PEWS score.

APPENDIX J

Permission Granted to Use BC PEWS

Theresa McElroy the author of the BC PEWS tool grants permission to Shelley Burke to use freely all aspects of the PEWS tool and information created by her. See email communication below.

From: McElroy, Theresa [VCH] [REDACTED]
Sent: Monday, February 24, 2020 9:13 AM
To: 'shelley' [REDACTED]
Cc: shburke@fullerton.edu
Subject: RE: PEWS Research article

Hi Shelley,
 Thank you for your email and kind words.

On our Child Health BC website, we have a wide variety of resources that you might find useful for your work: <https://www.childhealthbc.ca/initiatives/pediatric-early-warning-system-pews>
 If you click on the purple bar, you will see a number of clinical support tools.

We also have online training modules for PEWS if you click on PEWS in the formal learning section: <https://www.childhealthbc.ca/clinician-resources/formal-learning>

Good luck with your study. Happy to help further if you have questions.
 Warm regards,
 Theresa

Theresa McElroy, PhD, MIH, BScOT
Child Health BC Regional Coordinator, VCH & PHC
 604-601 W. Broadway Ave; Vancouver BC V5Z4C2
 Cell: 604-230-3557
 Fax: 604-875-4883

I acknowledge that the land on which we live, work, and play is the unceded territory of the Coast Salish peoples, including the territories of the x^wməθkwəy̓əm (Musqueam), Skwxwú7mesh (Squamish), and Səlílwətaʔ/Selilwiltulh (Tsleil-Waututh) Nations

From: shelley [REDACTED]
Sent: Saturday, February 22, 2020 9:01 AM
To: McElroy, Theresa [CWBC]
Cc: [REDACTED] shburke@fullerton.edu
Subject: PEWS Research article

Hello Ms. Theresa McElroy,

My name is Shelley Burke, I am a Registered Nurse, who is currently in a DNP (Doctor of Nursing Program) within the past six months, now starting the 2nd semester. I reside in Southern California, USA. I came across your research article on pediatric early warning system (PEWS), which would be the focus of my doctoral project. I would like to ask your permission to incorporate some of your teaching methodology into my write. I think you have done a wonderful job in this study on PEWS.

Let me know if that is ok with you. If you have any other resources, you deem beneficial to doing a PEWS project and would like to share, I will be happy to benefit from it.

Thanks for your time.

Shelley Burke, MSN, RN, CPN,
California State University Fullerton (CSUF)
shburke@fullerton.edu

Note. Permission was granted by Theresa McElroy of BC PEWS to use resources from her site in the development of this quality improvement *project*.

APPENDIX K

LAC+USC Letter of IRB Approval

Date: 06/30/2020

**Los Angeles County
Board of Supervisors**
Hilda L. Solis
First District

Mark Ridley-Thomas
Second District

Sheila Kuehl
Third District

Janice Hahn
Fourth District

Kathryn Barger
Fifth District

Jorge Orozco
Chief Executive Officer

Brad Spellberg, MD
Chief Medical Officer

Edgar Solis, RN
Chief Operations Officer

Isabel Milan, RN
Chief Nursing Officer

 1200 N. State Street
Inpatient Tower (IPT)
2nd Floor, Room C2K100
Los Angeles, CA 90033

 Tel: (323) 409-2800
Fax: (323) 441-8030

To ensure access to high-quality, patient-centered, cost-effective health care to Los Angeles County residents through direct services at DHS facilities and through collaboration with community and university partners.

 Department of Nursing
Los Angeles County + University of Southern California Medical Center
1200 N. State Street
Los Angeles, CA, 90033

To the Institutional Review Board(s) School IRB / USC

I am writing this letter at the request of student Shelley Burke to confirm that we are working with her as she commences her research project, "Pediatrics Early Warning Scores: A Quality Improvement Project."

I am aware that she will be conducting PEWS: Quality Improvement Project on Pediatrics, C8C, at LAC+USC Medical Center. Shelley Burke will have approval to such performance improvement project for as long as has IRB approval to do so.

I also confirm that employees here at LAC+USC Medical Center will not participate in the recruitment or selection of subjects, nor will they intervene with subjects by performing procedures, or by manipulating the environment for research purposes. Shelley Burke will have approval to do such procedures for as long as she has IRB approval to do so.

If any unanticipated problems or adverse events are to occur, it is up to Shelley Burke to report these events to the IRB at your school/USC and the LAC+USC Chief Nursing Officer / designee as promptly as possible.

Shelley Burke research will be a valuable contribution to the improvement of what your project does, and we will be happy to support this endeavor.

Please be prompt. If you have any questions, please contact me at 323-409-8841.

 Isabel Milan, RN, MBA
Chief Nursing Officer

Health Services
www.dhs.lacounty.gov

Note. IRB letter of approval from the CNO, granting the project author permission to conduct the quality improvement project at the project site.

APPENDIX L**CSUF IRB Approval Notice****CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, FULLERTON***Office of Research and Sponsored Projects*

P.O. Box 6850 or 1121 N. State College Blvd., 2nd Fl., Fullerton, CA 92831 / T 657-278-7719 / F 657-278-7238

APPROVAL NOTICE

*From the Institutional Review Board
California State University, Fullerton*

2020-10-23

From: Dr. Matt Englar-Carlson, Chair
CSUF Institutional Review Board

To: PI: Shelley Ann Burke

Application No. HSR-20-21-60

Study Title: Pediatrics Early Warning Scores (PEWS) Tool Implementation: A Quality Improvement Project on a Pediatric Unit

Re: Initial Exempt Review

The forms you submitted to this office regarding the use of human participants in the above-referenced proposal have been reviewed by the Regulatory Compliance Coordinator and the Chair of the California State University, Fullerton, Institutional Review Board. Your proposal is determined to be.

The CSUF IRB has not evaluated your proposal for scientific merit, except to weigh the risk to the human participants and the aspects of the proposal related to potential risk and benefit. This approval notice does not replace any departmental or additional approvals which may be

required.

It is of utmost importance that you strictly adhere to the guidelines for human participants and that you follow the plan/methodology/procedures described in your research proposal. Since your proposed was determined to be exempt, there is no further review or annual renewal required by the CSUF IRB. **However, any change in protocol or consent form procedure requires re-submission to the CSUF IRB for approval prior to implementation.** Additionally, the principal investigator must promptly report, in writing, any unanticipated or adverse events causing risks to research participants or others.

Please be advised that if you are seeking external funding for this proposal, the above-reference title should match exactly with the title submitted to the funding sponsor. Any changes in project title should be submitted to the CSUF IRB prior to implementation.

By copy of this notice, the chair of your department (and/or co-investigator) is reminded that their responsibility for being informed concerning research projects involving human participants in the department, and should review all protocols of such investigations as often as needed to ensure that the project is being conducted in compliance with our institutional policies and with DHHS regulations.

The institution has an Assurance on file with the Office of Human Research Protections. The Assurance Number is FWA00015384.

Cc: IRB Office
Asma Taha

Note. Notice of approval from the IRB at CSUF granting the project author permission to proceed with the quality improvement project proposal.